

4QAramaic Fragments in the PAM E-series

PAM photo	#	ms	frag	name	DJD vol
40965	1	4Q112	3i-ii*	4QDan^a	16
40963	32	4Q113	2	4QDan^b	16
40964	8	4Q114	2i*	4QDan^c	16
40985	3	4Q115	4	4QDan^d	16
40975	32	4Q115	5	4QDan^d	16
40982	23	4Q115	6	4QDan^d	16
40975	48	4Q115	7	4QDan^d	16
40974	37	4Q196	11	4QpapTob^a ar	19
40977	27	4Q196	29	4QpapTob^a ar	19
40974	54	4Q196	34	4QpapTob^a ar	19
40974	7	4Q196	12*	4QpapTob^a ar	19
40977	19	4Q196	14 i c	4QpapTob^a ar	19
40977	38	4Q196	14ii h*	4QpapTob^a ar	19
40974	3	4Q196	9*	4QpapTob^a ar	19
40977	66	4Q196	9*	4QpapTob^a ar	19
40964	12	4Q198	1*	4QTob^c ar	19
40976	5	4Q198	1*	4QTob^c ar	19
40985	11	4Q201	2	4QEn^a ar	BE
40976	50	4Q202	1iii u	4QEn^b ar	BE
40976	23	4Q202	1vi i'	4QEn^b ar	BE
40970	16	4Q202 ?		4QEn^b ar ?	
40975	8	4Q204	1 ii d*	4QEn^c ar	BE
40965	3	4Q204	1 v-vi g	4QEn^c ar	BE
40965	4	4Q204	1 v-vi i	4QEn^c ar	BE
40975	7	4Q204	1 vi g*	4QEn^c ar	BE
40978	77	4Q204	1 vi g*	4QEn^c ar	BE
40979	17	4Q204	1 vi g*	4QEn^c ar	BE
40975	13	4Q204	1 vi h	4QEn^c ar	BE
40965	2	4Q204	1 xii-xiii n	4QEn^c ar	BE
40982	53	4Q204	1ii*	4QEn^c ar	BE
40982	19	4Q204	1ve*	4QEn^c ar	BE
40963	23	4Q204	5 ii g	4QEn^c ar	BE
40979	42	4Q204	5 ii h	4QEn^c ar	BE
40978	26	4Q206	4i*	4QEn^e ar	BE
40978	34	4Q206	4iii f	4QEn^e ar	BE
40978	63	4Q213	1*	4QLevi^a ar	22
40976	34	4Q214b	1*	4QLevi^f ar	22
40964	27	4Q242	3	4QprNab ar	22
40978	3	4Q318	vii*	4QZodiology and Brontology ar	36
40974	40	4Q489	1	4QpapApocalypse ar	7
40965	8	4Q529	1	4QWords of Michael ar	31
40979	2	4Q530	17	4QEnGiants^b ar	31
40979	78	4Q531	3	4QEnGiants^c ar	31
40975	14	4Q531	4	4QEnGiants^c ar	31
40979	65	4Q531	29	4QEnGiants^c ar	31
40978	20	4Q531	37	4QEnGiants^c ar	31
40976	37	4Q541	11	4QapocrLevi^b? ar	31
40976	39	4Q541	13	4QapocrLevi^b? ar	31

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40976	38	4Q541	14	4QapocrLevi ^{b?} ar	31
40978	45	4Q543	23	4QVisAmram ^a	31
40979	81	4Q543	45	4QVisAmram ^a	31
40979	48	4Q543	1b	4QVisAmram ^a	31
40978	48	4Q543	1c	4QVisAmram ^a	31
40979	52	4Q543	2b	4QVisAmram ^a	31
40978	67	4Q543	33	4QVisAmram ^a	31
40978	86	4Q545	12+	4QVisAmram ^c	31
40965	6	4Q545	1a*	4QVisAmram ^c	31
40965	7	4Q545	1a*	4QVisAmram ^c	31
40965	5	4Q545	1b	4QVisAmram ^c	31
40978	52	4Q553	4	4QFourKingdoms ^b ar	37
40976	29	4Q553a	1	4QFourKingdoms ^c ar	37
40975	15	4Q556a	9	4QProphecy ^b ar	37
40974	20	4Q558	31	4QpapVision ^b ar	37
40972	5	4Q558	53	4QpapVision ^b ar	37
40977	28	4Q558	106	4QpapVision ^b ar	37
40977	37	4Q558	125+	4QpapVision ^b ar	37
40974	60	4Q558	50b	4QpapVision ^b ar	37
40977	18	4Q558	64*	4QpapVision ^b ar	37
40974	4	4Q559	12	4QpapBibChronology ar	37
40979	70	4Q570	16*	4QUnid. Text D ar	37
40963	34	4Q580	8	4QTestament ^a ar	37
40975	31	4Q584h	1	4QUnid. Frags. A ar	37